

Battery Management System using microcontroller

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1. Abstract

The Electric Vehicle (EV) is the goal of every car manufacturer and is seen as the solution to the most efficient transport system, which contributes to the major grooming problem of global warming by reducing gas emissions which lead to pollution.

The Energy Storage System (ESS) is the main component for EVs because it provides energy to all driving machines of EVs. This includes the battery and all the monitoring and management systems that compose the Battery Management System (BMS). Those batteries have very demanding requirements regarding safety, power density (acceleration), energy density (autonomy), high efficiency, deep discharge cycles, and low self-discharge rates to name a few.

The battery management system` (BMS) is the electronic control circuit that monitors and regulates the charging and discharge of batteries. The battery characteristics to be monitored include the name of battery type, capacity, power consumption, voltages, state of charge, temperature, remaining operating time, charging cycles, and some more characteristics.

The task of battery management systems is to take care of the battery such that it will work efficiently. To avoid loading the batteries, BMS systems protect the batteries from deep discharge, from over-voltage, which results from extremely fast charge and high discharge current. In the case of multi-cell batteries, the battery management system also provides a cell balancing function, to ensure that different battery cells have the same charging and discharging requirements.

The project focuses on designing and developing overload protection circuits for cell balancing.

2. Keywords

BMS, ESS, EV, Microcontroller, PIC, Relay Module, Arduino, battery, reliability, electrical.

3. Introduction

In this world of growing pollution and petrol rate rising crisis, it is very important to switch to electrical vehicles(EV). But switching toward electrical vehicles it is necessary to develop the parts and their components as it will increase our EV's efficiency. As Everyone knows the most important part of an EV is Battery. The reason is clear without energy we can do nothing with the machines. The Battery is the main device that drives the motor of our EV, but the battery needs to take care of. If proper care s

not taken then it will lead to a problem with our battery and we will have to replace it. So to increase the efficiency of the Battery Management System (BMS) is necessary.

4. Background

The BMS is a Device that carries out multiple functions like Cell Balancing, Overvoltage Protection, Undervoltage Protection, and many other things. Now for example the BMS will be simply understandable. Consider there are two cells with the charging of 3.8 V and 4 V and if we start their charging, then it is obvious that the cell with 4V will charge first and then 3.8 but till 3.8 is getting fully charged the 4V cell will get Overload and this will lead to degradation in the Battery life. In these cases, the BMS is the solution. This automatically removes the Cells from the Circuit that had already been charged. Now Considering the second condition, if a cell is discharged below its safe level then it will lead to an issue in its charging and simultaneously the efficiency will get dropped. This work is also carried out by the BMS. In this way, the BMS is necessary for our day-to-day life.

5. Existing System

In The existing system, there are BMS that operates supported IC dedicated to those respective Battery pack. We, Can't, use the BMS of 4S to 6S and that also aren't having more feature

6. Our proposal

The innovation which will add to the existing BMS is that it can be made programable, this may make it easy to use, and also it'll make it easy to convert any S rating BMS and another rated BMS. Also Adding a replacement feature in the BMS will also become easy. At the initial step, only the Balance Cell charging and voltage Rating display are achieved. this stuff is

achieved by those of a PIC microcontroller. the rationale behind using the PIC microcontroller is as follows: -

In the Microcontroller of PIC, multitasking is out there, and it operates as a strong processor. It also can be used in ports of ethernet, WIFI, Bluetooth, audio and video output, USB ports, camera ports, and other HDMI ports. Simple coding is additionally possible for the functioning of electronics. It also can be used to connect multiple components online to accomplish tasks simultaneously. Whereas Arduino, can execute just one code at a time if it runs any multiple codes, the system becomes slow.

7. Process

The process of making the project is divided into different steps: -

Step 1:

In this step, we initially gathered the knowledge based on the existing system of BMS. During this, the issues were noticed and likewise, the answer is decided and the problem is fixed.

Step 2:

After the full plan gets drafted, the step of selection of components is taken. While selecting the components all parameters must be taken into consideration.

Now moving toward each component's features and parameters: -

- PIC Microcontroller: 16F877A

PIC 16F877A(Peripheral Interface controller) :

The PIC controller is going to carry a very important part in our BMS of the

controller. This microcontroller is one of the most famous microcontrollers in the industry. This microcontroller is very efficient to use, and the coding or programming of this controller is also easier. The PIC Microcontroller has 40 pins. One of the advantages is that it can be write-erased as many times as possible because it uses FLASH memory technology. This microcontroller also has many applications in digital electronics circuits.

Fig 1: PIC 16F877A(1)

PIC16F877A finds its applications in many fields. It is used in security and safety devices, home automation, remote sensors, and many industrial instruments. By considering the factor of cost this microcontroller is cost efficient as well as easy to use. There is also a function of storing some of the information permanently like transmitter codes and receiver frequencies and some other related data due to the presence of EEPROM.

- The PIC microcontroller has 35 instructions set which are generally short in nature.
- It can operate up to 20MHz frequency which is more compared to AURDINO.

- The operating voltage of this IC is between 4.2 V to 5.5 V. If you provide it over-voltage(>5.5Volts) the IC gets damaged permanently.
- It doesn't have an internal oscillator like other PIC18F46K22, PIC18F4550.
- The maximum current that every PORT of this IC can sustain is around 100mA by this IC. Due to this reason, the current limit for each GPIO pin of the PIC Microcontroller is 10mA.
- It is out there in four IC packaging such as 44-pin PLCC, 40-pin PDIP, 44-pin TQFP, and 44-pin QFN.
- It consists of one 16-bit and two 8-bit timers.
- This PIC microcontroller present in the Capture and compare modules, serial ports, five input/output ports and parallel ports, are also present in it.
- The below picture shows the pinout diagram of PIC16F877A.

Fig 5.2: PIN Diagram PIC 16F877A(1)

Advantages of PIC Microcontroller:

- The PIC Microcontroller is more reliable due to its more Operating frequency And the performance of the PIC is very fast because of using RISC architecture.
- Power consumption is also very less when compared to other microcontrollers. When we see it from the programmer's point of view interfacing is very easy, also we can connect analog devices directly without any extra circuitry and use them. Programming of PIC microcontrollers is also easy as compared to other microcontrollers in the market.

B) 5V Relay Module

This is a 5V Relay Board Module For Arduino, PIC, AVR, DSP, and ARM. This is a relay of 1 Channel. Many microcontrollers such as Arduino, AVR, PIC, ARM, and so on can control it. Every module requires 15mA - 20mA driver current and Equipped with high current relay: DC 5V / 10A, AC 250V / 10A.

Fig 2 Relay Module (2)

The interface is standard that can be compatible with microcontrollers.

Specification and Features: -

- 1 channel relay board
- Operating Voltage: 5V
- Maximum Current: 20mA
- Relay Contact Current Capacity at AC 250V: 10A whereas at DC 5V:10A
- One NC contact and one NO contact is present in this RELAY MODULE.
- It has a Pull-down circuit for the avoidance of malfunction
- Power supply indicator lamp(Red).
- Control indicator lamp(Green).
- Indicator for Relay output status
- It can Be controlled by various appliances & other Equipment With a Large current.
- TTL Level Standard logic controlled (Arduino, 8051, AVR, PIC, ARM)

C) Voltage sensor

A voltage sensor is a device that is used to calculate and monitor the amount of voltage in a circuit. The Voltage sensors can determine the DC voltage or AC voltage level. The input of this sensor is the voltage which is analog in nature, whereas the output is in the form of digital.

Fig 3: Voltage sensor (3)

- Voltage input range of Sensor: DC 0 to

25 V

- Voltage detection range of this module: DC 0.02445V - 25 V Voltage
- Analog resolution (in Volt): 0.00489 V

D) Lithium-ion Battery:

Li-ion batteries usually have a high energy density compared to other energy sources, and the advantage of low self-discharge. This battery is a type of rechargeable battery in nature composed of cells in which lithium ions move from the negative electrode through an electrolyte to the positive electrode during discharge and back during the course of charging. This type of cell uses an intercalated material known as lithium compound at the portion of the positive electrode and typically graphite at the portion of the negative electrode. Cells can be manufactured on our requirements such as to prioritize either energy or power density. As these cells comprise flammable electrolytes if get damaged or incorrectly charged can lead to explosions and fires. The battery selected for this project:

Orange ICR 18650 2000mAh (3c) Lithium-Ion Battery

Fig 4: Li-ion Cell(4)

Specification of our selected battery :

- Capacity (mAh) of our cell: 2000
- Reference Voltage: 3.7V

- Charge Rate of Cell: 2C
- It usually has a high energy density.
It is Pollution-free in nature.
- It has a Long cycle life

Step 3:

After selection of the components, the circuit is designed in proteus8professional and simulated in the circuit. As the PIC microcontroller is used its programming is also necessary and the basic logic used by us for it programming is explained in flow chart as follows:-

Chart 1: Code Structure

As, the flow chart given above the programming is done in our PIC Microcontroller.

The main advantage of this circuit is that it discharges the cell in series and charges the cell in Parallel. After simulating the circuit, it is finalized.

Step 4:

Figure 1: BMS Circuit Diagram

In this final step, the circuit is tested.

8. Diagram

In this section with the help of simulation diagram we will carry testing of our BMS, We considered 4 cases to study how BMS responds to each case.

Case 1:

Both Cells are Disconnected as it is Sensed By The Voltage Sensor the value is 3V across each Cell. Here the Process of disconnection is carried by the help of relay. The logic is developed in our circuit is such that it makes circuit parallel in connection while charging and in series in discharging.

Figure 2

Case 2:

Only Second Cell is Disconnected and its charging is started as it is Sensed by the respective Voltage Sensor that only its value is 3V.

Figure 3

Case 3:

Only First Cell is Disconnected and its charging is started as it is Sensed By The respective Voltage Sensor that only its value is 3V.

Figure 4

Case 4:

When Both of The Cells Are Charged Results in a Change of Circuit from Charging to Discharging.

Figure 5

Advantages of BMS:

Figure 6: Venn Diagram

9. Result

In this project, the result is straightforward by use of a PIC Microcontroller the BMS is efficiently developed, which is programming friendly which makes it flexible to use. Based on the particular situation, different strategies

can be applied to upgrade and optimize the performance of BMS in EV'S.

- **Future Scope:**

The project is designed for a 2S battery pack (i.e. 2 cells in series). Now by using the same logic, it could be extended to N dumbbells Cell by using different types of BMS system types. Also, temperature protection can be added as it is also one of the important factors in BMS. So The feature which we can add to single BMS is the detection of battery type, voltages, temperature, capacity, state of charge, power consumption, remaining operating time, charging cycles, and some more characteristics.

10. Conclusion

In this way, the programmable BMS system model for battery management in electric vehicles by controlling the crucial parameters is developed. The BMS must be well maintained with battery reliability and safety. Moreover, the target of reducing greenhouse gases can greatly be achieved by using a battery management system. Because the battery is giving high efficiency the EV will also give high efficiency and simultaneously the pollution will get reduced. In this way, the Real purpose of EV can be utilized

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